

→ MESS0004: The Rapid growth of the EPEMC tree

MESS 0035

A Guide to EPEMC Trip Reports; past, present & future

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ABSTRACT

Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology^{1 2} has made rapid progress in the years since inception (2018). Evolutionarily, it has sprawled into many corners, and has gained many fans; as well as achieved unexpected status in Academia's social media ranking. The growth of podcast³ and shows⁴ with so many fans, is touching. But what is unsung, in importance, and key to the difference here and with almost all the altstream, saving perhaps the Zamora-Hancock-Schoch-Carlson cadre, is the performance of real site surveys using electromagnetometers, civil engineering equipment, drones, and other means of mapping; as well as demonstration of the issues. For example, videographic proof that Shiprock cannot possibly be 27 million years old, etc. In this paper we list these works, and put out a short road-map for the immediate future of the EPEMC[™], and encourage others to do the same.

Keywords: geology - meteorology - petroglyphs - rock art - plasmaglyphs - Arthurology - Kentucky - Arizona

¹ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC

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https://www.academia.edu/73271902/Paradigm_Shift_Comparison_EPEMC_vs_The_Rest_Comparing_PEMC_EU_PU_MU_and_SM_BSM

³ <https://rumble.com/c/c-1498071>

⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/home/shows>

Previous EPEMC Trip Reports & Site Surveys

Table 1 - Trip Reports by Author

<i>Site Survey or Trip Report</i>	<i>Topics / Scope of Work</i>	<i>Coordinates</i>
Mt. Horeb c-henge mound ⁵	Electromagnetic measure & map ⁶	38.158889, -84.465556
Garden of the Gods, IL	Photograph of polarized rock ⁷	37.606944, -88.394722
Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge, KY	Photograph of anti-stratigraphy	37.85842, -83.67155
Dogfoot Hollow, KY	Confirmatory photograph of A-S	37.53732, -84.21738
Shiprock, AZ	Photographic rock survey ⁸	36.6875, -108.836389
Culvertown, KY Platform	Full site survey ⁹ and drone imagery ¹⁰	37.70449, -85.5123
Caer Melyn (Camelot) ¹¹	Hi-res drone survey ¹²	51.54487, -3.28954
Lost City of Russellville, KY	Photographs only ¹³	36.9712, -86.91068
Grand Canyon, AZ	Photographs only ¹⁴	36.3, -112.6
Barringer Crater, AZ	Videographic Examination of core	35.028056, -111.023333
Pine Mountain, KY	Extensive survey and Study ¹⁵	36.948611, -83.182222
Three Rivers Petroglyphs, NM	Photographs of plasmaglyphs ¹⁶	33.346944, -106.011667
Graffiti Rock, KY	Photographs of modern	37.52261, -84.23019

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

⁶ Ramon Careaga - New Discovery in LiDAR Readings at Big Sink

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/81402498/Trip_Report_Shiprock_and_Barringer_Crater

⁹ https://www.academia.edu/37817203/Trip_Report_Culvertown_Platform_Formation

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/49439216/Trip_Report_Culvertown_Platform_Addendum

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https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

¹² <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1swp3vOix2leTQjFQgcS--0pX8KHBUEMd?usp=sharing>

¹³ Avalon Arthurology in the 21st Century

¹⁴ 20220516_161042_HDR.jpg

¹⁵ MESS0020: GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's Crooked Smile Hypothesis Proven by the Pine Mountain flux

¹⁶ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1dmZtvL78Rw5X3v-rZp_YVUy3wN1OaIzD?usp=share_link

	plasmaglyphic evidence ¹⁷	
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Table 2 - cont'd, not by Author

Upheaval Dome, UT	Site observation and study/paper ¹⁸	

Present

The present work have been primarily transparent overlays and use of software, mapping, and weather technology (to look at Changes¹⁹ and electrogeometerology) to create MESSies²⁰. The result of this work has been more than satisfactory because it is macrolytic and conforms to a *general* mimsical-diagrammatica. However, in the world of EPEMC [graded] evidence, it is not enough. Therefore, some of the future work will push the inclusion of other site surveys. The author also has a pending Trip Report due about Three Rivers Petroglyphs and also about Graffiti Rock, KY. These need to be produced back to back for a MESSy to then be produced based upon these works.

Future

The most immediate future goal is another electromagnetic site survey for WinStar farms in the area of the Perattian Thunderbolt. Also, site surveys for Pebble Beach and Culvertown would be excellent. Here are other ideas for near term future site surveys and trip reports:

- WinStar Farms - single crater
- Lily Cornett Woods vs. Pine Mountain Flux electromagnetics
- Redbird Forest
- Crystal Onyx Cave
- Access to Ft. Knox for the Dome on base
- Fluoropsar District/mine
- Photographs of the stone mounds beneath Yatesville Lake
- Lawrence County "serpent mound"

¹⁷ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/10lgGVrnk7FYPLHE42pNFooezl1H6FZd9?usp=share_link

¹⁸ <https://www.iiisci.org/journal/pdv/sci/pdfs/ZA014LF20r.pdf>

¹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/80123254/MIMS_2_2_5_1_Applying_Change_Theory

²⁰ [MESS0018: GEO 2.2 - Magnetic Anomalies in VA and KY](#)

[MESS0019: MET 2.1 - KY Tornado New Madrid Zone & magnetics](#)

[MESS0021: GEO 2.22 - New Madrid Zone and Blue Ridge: Magmaflux](#)

[MESS0022: GEO 2.23 - Freshwater/Groundwater table analysis vs. anomalies](#)

[MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME](#)

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